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Tax Revenue Streams and Nigeria's Manufacturing Sector Output: Empirical Insights on the 2025 Tax Reforms Act

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ABSTRACT

The study evaluated the effect of tax revenue streams on the Nigeria's manufacturing sector output from first quarter of 2012 to fourth quarter of 2024. The study placed emphasis on the 2025 Tax Reform Act. Three tax revenue streams considered are value added tax (VAT), company income tax (CIT), and hydrocarbon tax (HCT) while manufacturing sector output (MSQ) was measured using the aggregate contribution of oil refining, cement, food, Beverage and Tobacco, Textile, Apparel and Paper products, wood and wood products, pulp, paper and paper products, chemical and pharmaceutical product, non-metallic products, basic metal, iron and steel, motor vehicles and assembly, and other manufacturing to GDP. This study used a quantitative approach while the data were sourced from the National Bureau of Statistics, Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin spanning from the first quarter of 2012 to first quarter of 2024. The robust regression analysis (ARMA Maximum Likelihood) estimate reported that VAT revenue stream has a positive and significant effect on MSQ. Conversely, CIT revenue stream has a negative insignificant effect on MSQ. Meanwhile, HCT revenue stream has a negative insignificant effect on MSQ. Hence, the paper concludes that VAT and low HCT are highly beneficial to the Nigeria's manufacturing sector. To further enhance VAT revenue stream, policy makers should ensure that better tax compliance and base broadening is encouraged. Also, the proposition by the 2025 Tax Reform Act to gradually increase the VAT rate from 7.5% to 15% by 2030 should be sustained. In like manner, there is need to revisit the corporate tax structures, especially for the manufacturing sector. Lastly, revenue from petroleum products and natural gas should be reinvested into manufacturing sector to offset the adverse effects HCT has on MSQ.

Keywords: Tax Revenue streams, Value Added Tax, Hydrocarbon Tax, Federal Inland Revenue Service

1. INTRODUCTION

Globally, the manufacturing sector play strategic roles in the economy as it drives technological innovation, creates job opportunities for able-bodied individuals, and reduces the country's dependency ratio (Effiong & Udonwa, 2024). In Nigeria, the sector has been conceived as a source of economic diversification away from oil and as a mechanism for the attainment of sustainable development

(Ndiomaluke et al., 2025). Despite these prospects, the manufacturing sector's contribution to the Nigerian Gross Domestic Product (GDP) has remained low and unstable, reflecting a variety of structural and policy challenges (Onoshole, 2024). Among them is the fiscal space (tax revenue), which is directly involved in influencing the manufacturing sector's performance (Oyerogba et al., 2024).

Tax revenue streams, as a major fiscal operation measure, serves as major strategy adopted by the government to bridge a country's domestic-investment gap (Joshua-Gyang, 2024). Common measures of tax revenues are Company Income Tax (CIT), Value Added Tax (VAT), and hydrocarbon tax (HCT) (Olika et al., 2024). While tax revenues are essential for improving and financing the public sector, they also impose costs on business firms (Olubunmi et al., 2025). Justifiably, well-designed tax system improves the manufacturing sector's output through funding necessary infrastructure and enabling economic activities. However, an inefficiently administered tax regime can discourage production, reduce competitiveness, and deter investment in the manufacturing industry (Nnah, 2024; Ubali et al., 2024).

Nevertheless, there has been an ongoing debate regarding the nexus between tax revenue and manufacturing sector output (Oyerogba et al., 2024; Fijabi et al., 2024). While some tax scholars evidenced that optimally administered tax collections stimulate the growth of the manufacturing sector through the provision of enabling business environment and improved infrastructural development (Joshua-Gyang, 2024; Olika et al., 2024), other scholars reported that excessive tax rate reduces the sector's output by increasing the cost of doing business and creating harsh business environment for domestic and foreign investors (Yanto et al., 2025; Bilan & Apostoaie, 2025; Agama et al., 2024; Ikpe et al., 2024; Okezie, 2024). This divergence in scholarly perspectives suggests that the impact of tax revenue on manufacturing sector output is context-specific.

In response to the above contrasting views, it is highly imperative to conduct sector-specific empirical evidence on how tax revenue influence the Nigerian manufacturing sector's output. Specifically, the paper evaluated the effect of company income tax (CIT), value added tax (VAT) and hydrocarbon tax (HCT) individually and jointly influence the Nigeria manufacturing sector output from 2012Q1 to 2024Q1. Hence, this study goes beyond earlier tax studies by providing a disaggregated view of how each tax revenue proxies affect the output of the Nigerian manufacturing sector during the specified periods. Furthermore, the study contributes to the ongoing tax policy discourse by providing a robust empirical evidence of its relevance on industrial development of Nigeria. By using a quarterly data approach, the study was able to capture the post-oil shock experience and also stressed on the necessity of evidence-based tax policy formulation targeted at improving the output of the Nigerian manufacturing sector.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS FORMULATION

2.1. Tax Revenues and Manufacturing Sector Output

Tax revenues are key fiscal policy measures (Vom Hau et al., 2023). Broadly speaking, tax revenue comprises direct and indirect taxes. Common measure of direct tax is company income tax (CIT) while common measures of indirect tax are value added tax (VAT) and customs and excise duties (CED). These taxes served as income redistributive mechanism targeted at either enhancing or discouraging economic productivity (Boar & Midrigan, 2022; Yang et al., 2024; Nguyen, & Darsono, 2022). On the other hand, manufacturing sector output (MSO) refers to the aggregate contributions of manufacturing sector to a country's gross domestic products (GDP) during a specified period of time (Prasad et al., 2023; Gabardo et al., 2017; Adejumo et al., 2020). It therefore cut across the contribution of oil refining, cement, food, Beverage and Tobacco, Textile, Apparel and Paper products, wood and wood products, pulp, paper and paper products, chemical and pharmaceutical product, non-metallic products, basic metal, iron and steel, motor vehicles and assembly, and other manufacturing to GDP (CBN, 2024).

2.2. Value Added Tax Revenue Stream and Manufacturing Sector Output

Value Added Tax (VAT) is a consumption tax on goods and services levied at each stage of the supply chain where value is added. Although VAT is a consumption tax borne by final consumers in the long run, it has implications for manufacturing companies in relation to compliance costs, cash flows, and room for adaptability to changes in consumers' demand. According to the Incidence Theory of Taxation

(Mascagni et al., 2023), economic incidence of VAT can be shifted to producers or consumers depending on the shape of demand and market form. Ramsey Rule of optimum theory of taxation implies that commodities with inelastic demands need to be taxed in order to minimize efficiency losses, and it can be used for industrial commodities with given demand structures. Empirical evidence regarding VAT impact on manufacturing performance is varied across contexts. While Odu (2022) and Akpokhio & Ekperiware, (2022) are in the view that VAT distorts manufacturing activity via the vehicle of rising cost of production, Olika et al., (2024) affirm that when VAT collections are directed towards investment in infrastructure and regulatory services, they buoy sectoral output. Drawing on lessons from the two perspectives, the study postulates that:

H₁: Value Added Tax revenue stream has a significant effect on Nigeria's MSQ

2.3. Company Income Tax Revenue Stream and Manufacturing Sector Output

Company Income Tax (CIT) Revenue Stream is a statutory tax on a firm's net income (Akpokhio & Ekperiware, 2022). Although, CIT is a vital source of state income, it is also a burden to the profitability of firms. The two major theories which give clear view on the effect of CIT on sectorial outputs are the neoclassical investment theory and the Public Finance Theory. The Neoclassical Investment Theory argues that higher corporate taxation raises the user cost of capital and thus deters investment and reduces output (Boadway 1980). However, the public finance theory argues that where public revenues are well spent on the delivery of public services, public infrastructure, and economic management, the revenues are likely to generate a climate reversing the adverse effect of taxation (Tresch, 2022). Empirical findings regarding the nexus between CIT and industrial performance are varied. Moran et al. (2021) and Shaqiri et al. (2024) believe that higher corporate tax rates significantly lower productivity and investment, while Oguejiofor et al. (2023) believe that open tax systems and efficient government spending can eliminate the negative impact of CIT on industrial performance. Grounded on these theoretical and empirical findings, the paper derives the following hypothesis:

H₂: Company Income Tax Revenue Stream has a significant effect on Nigeria's MSQ

2.4. Hydrocarbon Tax Revenue Stream and Manufacturing Sector Output

Hydrocarbon Tax (HCT) revenue streams are the taxes which are imposed on the exploitation (extraction), production, and sales of natural gas and crude oil. This revenue stream is designed to ensure that the public sector (government) captures a share of revenue stream from the exploitation of hydrocarbon resources. Unlike consumption taxes such as VAT and HCT target upstream petroleum operations (George-Anokwuru, 2023). The main objective of HCT is to optimize revenue generation from hydrocarbon activities while promoting accountability, transparency, and environmental responsibility in the oil and gas rich sector (Delamou, 2025). Similarly, hydrocarbon taxes serve not only as a revenue stream but also as an efficient fiscal policy tool for managing environmental externalities, regulating resource extraction, and fostering economic diversification (Antwi-Boateng & Al Harasi, 2025; Igwe, 2025; Xiaolei, 2025).

Theoretically, the imposition of HCT conforms to environmental fiscal policy and the resource rent theory. The environmental fiscal policy theory emphasizes the need to internalize the social and environmental costs associated with hydrocarbon exploitation, while encouraging sustainable development and economic diversification (Saqib et al, 2023). Likewise, the Resource rent theory stressed that it is expedite for the government to share of the economic rents derived from the extraction of natural resources since it is a social goods (Hassan et al, 2025; Bougiatiotis, 2025; Kumar, 2025). Consequently, the study hypothesizes that:

H₃: Hydrocarbon Tax Revenue Stream has a significant effect on Nigeria's MSQ

3. METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative approach with emphasis on the ex post facto research design. The reason for choosing this approach stems from the fact that the variables of interest are historical data. Data used

for the analysis are CIT, VAT, HCT and MSQ. These variables were retrieved from the National Bureau of Statistics, Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS), and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin spanning from the first quarter of 2012 (2012Q1) to first quarter of 2024 (2024Q1). The census sampling technique was adopted since our population equals our sample size. The robust regression served as the main estimation technique used to analyze the three (3) research hypotheses earlier formulated. This estimation approach was justifiably chosen to address the adverse influence which violations of normality and Heteroskedasticity assumptions have on the validity of the regression estimate. By reducing these limitations, this estimation technique provides more robust parameter estimates than conventional OLS estimates.

In estimating the robust regression model, preliminary tests such as descriptive tests, normality tests, correlation analysis, multicollinearity tests, heteroscedasticity and model specification test were done to test the suitability of the robust regression estimate. The robust regression framework allows for consistent estimation of both the individual and jointly effects of CIT, VAT, and HCT on manufacturing sector output. The implicit form of our model is expressed in Equation 3.1as:

$$MSO = f(CIT, VAT, HCT) \text{ ----- 3.1}$$

Where:

- MSO** = Manufacturing Sector Output,
- CIT** = Company Income Tax,
- VAT** = Value Added Tax, and
- HCT** =Hydrocarbon Tax.

Although Equation 1 provides the basic linear specification of the functional relationship between manufacturing sector output (MSQ) and tax revenue proxies (CIT, VAT, & HCT), the explicit form is preferred due to its econometric and superior interpretive properties. Consequently, the explicit linear model (i.e. econometric model) is stated in Equation 3.2 as:

$$MSQ = \beta_0 + \beta_1CIT + \beta_2VAT + \beta_3HCT + \varepsilon_t \text{ ----- 3.2}$$

To reduce the possibility of presence of scaling and heteroskedasticity problems, both the tax revenue and manufacturing sector output proxies were transformed into their natural logarithmic forms with a view to minimize the effects of scale differences among the variables, stabilize the variance of the series, and enhance the interpretability of the estimated coefficients. The log-linear explicit model form is specified in Equation 3.3 as:

$$\ln(MSQ_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1\ln(CIT_t) + \beta_2\ln(VAT_t) + \beta_3\ln(HCT_t) + \varepsilon_t \text{ ----- 3.3}$$

Where:

- ln(MSO_t)** = Transformed (logged) value of MSO at time t,
- ln(CIT_t)** = Transformed (logged) value of CIT at time t,
- ln(VAT_t)** = Transformed (logged) value of VAT at time t,
- ln(HCT_t)** = Transformed (logged) value of HCT at time t,
- β₀** = Constant,
- β₁, β₂, β₃** = Coefficient.
- ε_t** = Error term (unobserved influences).

For purposes of clarity and transparency, Table 1 captures how each variables is operationalized, the justifications and apriori expectations:

Table 1: Variable Measurement and APriori Expectations

S/N	Variable	Denotation	Nature	Measurement/Operationalization	Apriori Expectation
1	Manufacturing Sector Output	MSQ	Dependent	Aggregate contribution of oil refining, cement, food, Beverage and Tobacco, Textile, Apparel and Paper products, wood and wood products, pulp, paper and paper products, chemical and pharmaceutical product, non-metallic products, basic metal, iron and steel, motor vehicles and assembly, and other manufacturing in GDP quarterly	Nil
2	Company Income Tax	CIT	Independent	Aggregate CIT revenue collected quarterly	Negative (-)
3	Value Added Tax	VAT	Independent	Aggregate VAT revenue collected quarterly	Positive (+)
4	Hydrocarbon Tax	HCT	Independent	Aggregate revenue from Petroleum and Natural Gas Tax quarterly	Negative (-)

Source: Researcher's Compilation (2025)

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

This section of the article focused on the presentation of the result output and the discussion of the empirical findings. Specifically, this section assessed the effect of tax revenue on manufacturing sector's output in Nigeria from quarter one of 2012 to quarter of 2024 using Generalized Least Square (GLS) approach. The various preliminary tests conducted are summary statistics, normality test, correlation analysis (Pearson correlation), multi-collinearity tests, Heteroskedasticity tests, Ramsey Reset tests, and Breusch Pagan LM tests. Each is discussed thus:

Table 2: Summary Statistics (N=52)

Variables	Mean	Maximum	Minimum	Std. Dev.
MSQ	1585.020	1824.920	1169.050	151.7178
VAT	473.6660	1946.830	170.6900	417.2537
CIT	353.5152	778.3000	15.89000	167.3880
HCT	547.0521	1608.340	31.90000	294.0805

Note: Manufacturing Sector's Output (MSQ); Value Added Tax (VAT); Company Income Tax (CIT); and Hydrocarbon Tax (HCT)

As presented in Table 2, the summary statistics recorded 52 observations (2012Q1 to 2024Q4). The average MSQ stood at ₦1585.02 billion but deviated by ₦151.72 billion, suggesting moderate variability. In like manner, the least MSQ value recorded was ₦1169.05 billion while the highest MSQ values from 2012Q1 to 2024Q4 was ₦1824.92 billion. However, an average VAT revenue value of ₦473.67 billion was recorded between 2012Q1 to 2024Q4 but significantly fluctuated by ₦417.25 billion. Similarly, the least VAT value recorded was ₦170.69 billion while the highest VAT value recorded from 2012Q1 to 2024Q4 was ₦1946.83 billion. Additionally, CIT recorded an average value of ₦353.52 billion, with a moderate standard deviation value of ₦167.39 billion and showed highest and least CIT values of ₦778.30 billion and ₦15.89 billion, respectively. Lastly, HCT reported average value of ₦547.05 billion with a low standard deviation value of 294.08. More so, the least HCT value recorded from 2012Q1 to 2024Q4 was ₦15.89000 was while the highest HCT value recorded from 2012Q1 to 2024 Q4 was ₦778.3000 billion. The uneven trends in tax revenue streams and MSQ recorded from 2012Q1 to 2024Q4

justify the need for a robust time-series analysis to understand their dynamic interactions and influence on MSQ.

Table 3: Normality Test

Variables	Jarque-Bera	Probability	Interpretation
MSQ	12.96591	0.001529	Deviated from Normality Assumption
VAT	69.61005	0.000000	Deviated from Normality Assumption
CIT	2.362998	0.306818	Normally Distributed
HCT	18.55421	0.000094	Deviated from Normality Assumption

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

From Table 3, the Jarque-Bera test was conducted to test the normality of the distribution of each variable. Specifically, MSQ, VAT, and HCT reported a Jarque-Bera value of 12.96591, 69.61005, 2.362998, and 18.55421 and associated p-values of 0.0015, 0.0000, and 0.0001 respectively. This suggests that MSQ, VAT, and HCT deviated significantly from the normality assumption. However, CIT is normally distributed. The violation of normality of MSQ, VAT, and HCT suggests that relying on conventional least square estimate may not yield efficient outcome for policy formulation. Consequently, the Normality estimate is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Normality Test

From Figure 1, a Jarque-Bera value of 2.983326 was recorded, with an associated p-value of 0.224998 ($p > 0.05$). This suggests that the model is normally distributed having re-modified the model.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation Analysis

Sample: 2012Q1 2024Q4
Included observations: 52

Correlation Observations	MSQ	VAT	CIT	HCT
MSQ	1.000000			
VAT	0.415361	1.000000		
CIT	0.103321	0.361571	1.000000	
HCT	-0.218705	0.296296	-0.142230	1.000000

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025)

The Pearson correlation analysis as shown in Table 4, VAT has a moderate positive correlation with MSQ ($r = 0.415$) and that such relationship is moderate. This suggests that rise in VAT

revenues are associated with improved MSQ. Similarly, CIT reported a weak positive correlation with MSQ ($r = 0.103$), suggesting that CIT has a marginal correlation with MSQ. Conversely, HCT exhibits a weak negative correlation with MSQ ($r = -0.219$). This suggests that increases in HCT reduce MSQ marginally. Nevertheless, none of the tax revenue streams reported high correlation with each other. These correlation values however, justify need to test for multicollinearity using Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) and Tolerance Value (TOV) as advanced by Enakirerhi and Ighosewe (2024). The results are presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Multi-collinearity Tests

Multi-collinearity	VAT	CIT	HCT	Average
VIF	1.340737	1.248283	1.18952	1.2595
TOV	0.7459	0.8011	0.8407	0.7959

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025); Note: VIF=Variance Inflation Factors; TOV=Tolerance Values

From Table 5, the VIF values of VAT, CIT, and HCT are below 5, and TOVs is above 0.1, indicating that tax revenue stream measures did not exhibit multicollinearity problems.

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity Test

Conventional Least Estimate		Robust Regression Estimate	
F-statistic	Prob. F(3,48)	F-statistic	Prob. F(3,48)
4.299112	0.0091	0.940348	0.4286

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 6, the conventional least square estimate reported an F-statistic value of 4.299112 and a Prob. F(3,48) value of 0.0091 suggesting that the residuals of the conventional least square estimate spreads unequally (i.e. Heteroskedastic). This confirmed that the model is not fit for policy formulation. To address this challenge, the model was further subjected to robust regression analysis. As re-specified, the model reported an F-statistic value of 0.940348 and a Prob. F(3,48) value of 0.4286, suggesting that the model spreads equally (i.e. Homoskedastic).

Table 7: Model Specification (Ramsey RESET) Test

Conventional Least Estimate		Robust Regression Estimate	
F-statistic	Prob. F(1,45)	F-statistic	Prob. F(1,45)
4.491078	0.0394	1.310036	0.2584

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 7, the model specification (Ramsey RESET) test reported an F-statistic value of 4.491078 and a Prob. F (1, 45) value of 0.0394 in the case of Model 1. This suggests that the model is not well-specified. To address this challenge, the model was re-specified. The re-specified model reported an F-statistic value of 1.310036 and a Prob. F (1, 45) value of 0.2584, suggesting that the model is correctly specified.

Table 8: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

Conventional Least Estimate			Robust Regression Estimate
F-statistic	Prob. F(1,45)	Durbin-Watson stat	Durbin-Watson stat
16.97388	0.0002	0.829764	2.013920

Source: Researcher's Computation (2025)

From Table 8, the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test reported an F-statistic value of 16.97388 and a Prob. F (1,45) value of 0.0002 in the case of Model 1. This suggests that the model is serially correlated. To further confirm this, the model reported a Durbin-Watson test of 0.829764. To address this challenge, the model was re-specified. The re-specified model reported Durbin-Watson test of 2.013920, suggesting that the model is free from serial correlation.

Regression Analysis

Table 1 to 8 above justified the need for a robust regression analysis other than the conventional regression analysis. The estimate of the robust regression is presented thus in Table 9.

Table 9: ARMA Maximum Likelihood (OPG - BHHH)

Regressed: MSQ Sample: 2012Q1 2024Q4 (52 Observation); Converged After 21 Iterations				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.167296	0.232856	30.77999	0.0000*
VAT	0.170950	0.069353	2.464914	0.0175**
CIT	-0.027928	0.020160	-1.385338	0.1726
HCT	-0.180011	0.072968	-2.466973	0.0172**
AR(1)	0.636500	0.110593	5.755348	0.0000*
SIGMASQ	0.004588	0.001239	3.703615	0.0006*
Model Summary Output				
R ²	0.552500	Adj. R ²	0.503859	
Durbin-Watson stat	2.013920	Mean dependent Var	7.363456	
F-statistic	11.35867	Prob (F-statistic)	0.000000	

Source: Researcher’s Computation (2025); Note: * and **denote Significance at 1% and 5% levels respectively

The robust regression analysis (ARMA Maximum Likelihood) estimate presented in Table 9 provide useful insights into the dynamic relationship between tax revenue streams (VAT, CIT, and HCT) and MSQ from 2012Q1 to 2024Q4. Specifically, the result confirmed that the constant term (C) is both positive and statistically significant at the 1% level ($\beta = 7.167$; $p < 0.01$). This indicates a strong baseline level of MSQ in the absence of the tax revenue streams (VAT, CIT, and HCT). Meanwhile, both the unadjusted and adjusted R² values (unadjusted R²=55.25% and adjusted R² =50.39%) confirmed that tax revenue streams (VAT, CIT, and HCT) explained over 50% variations in MSQ revalidating that the model has a high predictive power.

Among the tax revenue stream measures, VAT revenue stream has a positive and significant effect on MSQ ($\beta = 0.170950$; p-value = 0.0175). This implies that a unit increases in VAT revenue leads to 0.170950 increases in MSQ and effect of such increase is statistically significant at 5% significant level. Hypothesis one is therefore supported and its alternate rejected. The policy implication of this outcome is that VAT revenue stream contributes positively to MSQ. This further confirmed that VAT revenue stream is a meaningful and impactful tax revenue stream with a tangible economic beneficial effect on MSQ. This confirmed that improving the VAT stream does not only improve the public revenue base but also drive measurable improvements in MSQ, reinforcing the need for sustaining VAT-centered tax reform strategies. This outcome confirms the decision to gradually increase the VAT from 7.5% to 15% by 2030, as outlined in the 2025 Tax Reform Act signed by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu on 26th June, 2025, is a step in the right direction. Theoretically, the outcome revalidates the theoretical positions of both the optimal taxation and Keynesian fiscal intervention suggesting that fiscal tools (VAT revenue stream) can stimulate economic outcomes (MSQ) significantly.

Conversely, CIT revenue stream has a negative insignificant effect on MSQ ($\beta = -0.0279$; p-value = 0.1726). This implies that 1% increase in CIT revenue stream leads to a 2.79% reduction in MSQ, but the effect is marginal. Hypothesis two is therefore rejected and its alternate accepted. The policy implication of this outcome is that currently CIT exerts a mild retarding effect on MSQ. This outcome underscores the need to revisit corporate tax structures, especially for the manufacturing sector. While the outcome diverges from the Keynesian fiscal intervention predictions, it aligns with position of the optimal taxation theory. Thus, improving CIT revenue stream to avoid distortionary effects remains key fiscal policy toll for maximizing tax effectiveness without retarding MSQ. In relation to 2025 Tax Reform Act, the decision to increase CIT rate beyond 30% will distort the productive sector.

Lastly, HCT revenue stream has a negative insignificant effect on MSQ ($\beta = -0.180011$; p-value = 0.0172). This implies that 1% increase in HCT revenue stream leads to an 18% reduction in MSQ, but the effect is high. Also, hypothesis three is therefore rejected and its alternate accepted. The policy implication of this outcome is that, high HCT has a significant retarding effect on MSQ. This suggests that over-reliance on revenue from crude oil and natural gas will have devastating effect on MSQ. Although, both the environmental fiscal policy and the resource rent theory aligns with our findings in principle but underscores the need for strategic reinvestment of those rents (revenue from petroleum products and natural gas) into manufacturing sector to offset the adverse effects HCT has on MSQ. By implication, if resource rents are channeled into manufacturing sector, the over-reliance on the extractive industries will be reduced. This approach will also hedge against the volatility of crude oil prices (Saqib et al, 2023; Hassan et al, 2025; Bougiatiotis, 2025; Kumar, 2025).

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The study evaluated the effect of tax revenue streams on manufacturing sectors output in Nigeria from first quarter of 2012 to fourth quarter of 2024 using the ARMA model. The study placed emphasis on the 2025 Tax Reform Act. The study concludes that VAT and low HCT are highly beneficial to the Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Consequently, various policy measures were proposed with a view to enhancing the contribution of tax revenue streams on the output of the Nigeria's manufacturing sector. To further enhance VAT revenue stream, policy makers should ensure that better tax compliance and base broadening is encouraged. Also, the proposition by the 2025 Tax Reform Act to gradually increase the VAT rate from 7.5% to 15% by 2030 should be sustained. In like manner, the decision to increase CIT rate beyond 30% will distort the productive sector, is a step in the right direction and that it should be sustained. Again, there is need to revisit the corporate tax structures, especially for the manufacturing sector. Lastly, revenue from petroleum products and natural gas should be reinvested into manufacturing sector to offset the adverse effects HCT has on MSQ.

This study adds to the extant tax policy literature by offering empirical evidence on the differing effects of various tax revenue streams (VAT, CIT, and HCT) on Nigeria's MSQ. The study advanced previous tax policy studies by providing empirical insights on the usefulness of ARMA in ascertaining the dynamic relationship between tax revenue stream and MSQ. Further, the study advanced theoretical debates by distinguishing the growth-enhancing role of broadened VAT from the distortionary impact of high CIT and HCT rates on the Nigeria's manufacturing sector. Lastly, the study provides empirical justification on the new Tax Reform Act. Nevertheless, the study fails to do a comparative analysis on the effect of tax revenue streams on various sectors' output in Nigeria. This will yield more granular insights into how tax revenue streams sector respond to various sectors' output. There is also need to be integrated the impact of structural breaks and global economic shocks into the tax revenue stream model as this would better reflect real-world complexities. Similarly, future research should include other relevant tax revenue stream measures such as custom and exercise duties, stamp duties and education tax into the tax revenue stream model. Lastly, future researches should adopt more advanced econometric techniques such Threshold Regression, Nonlinear ARDL models and Vector Error Correction Models (VECM). This will enhance the methodological contributions of future studies by uncovering the threshold and non-linear effects of tax revenue streams on MSQ.

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